

EFFECT OF FUNCTIONALIZATION AND ADDING METHOD OF CARBON NANOTUBE ON INTERLAMINAR PROPERTY OF CARBON FIBER/EPOXY COMPOSITE

Mengsi Zhang^{*1}, Yizhuo Gu¹, Yujiao Fan¹, Min Li¹, Shaokai Wang¹, Zuoguang Zhang¹

¹Key Laboratory of Aerospace Advanced Materials and Performance (Ministry of Education),
School of Materials Science and Engineering, Beihang University, Beijing, China.

Email: zhangmengsi@buaa.edu.cn, web page: <http://www.buaa.edu.cn>

Key words: carbon nanotube; composite laminate; carbon fiber/epoxy prepreg; interlaminar fracture toughness; autoclave process

ABSTRACT

Using carbon nanotubes (CNTs) to toughen polymer and its fiber reinforced composites has been extensively studied, but the selection of nanotube and preparation process optimization still lack adequate theoretical support and data basis. Meanwhile, most researches adopted CNTs to modify polymer prepared in laboratory, rather than ones with high performances in practical application. This paper provided a research on an aerospace grade carbon fibers/epoxy composite system which has been used in practice, and proved the feasibility of toughening composite by CNTs.

CNTs modified epoxy resin was prepared by directly adding non-functionalized CNTs, carboxyl-CNTs and amino-CNTs into resin, respectively. The resin was used to prepare carbon fiber prepreg, and the laminates were cured by autoclave process. Adding carboxyl-CNTs increases Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness of composite laminate evidently, but all kinds of CNTs show no significant effect on Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness, which is related to the distribution and orientation of CNTs. Furthermore, the influences of CNTs on resin properties and the interface between carbon fiber and resin were evaluated. The results show that adding CNTs increases the resin viscosity, and decreases the degree of curing reaction. The carboxyl-CNTs greatly enhance the interfacial bonding strength due to chemical reaction with sizing agent of carbon fiber. Moreover, spraying the carboxyl-CNTs on the surface of prepreg was applied to prepare composite laminates, and larger improving degree on interlaminar property than that with directly dispersing the CNTs in resin is found. It is attributed to the high utilization degree of CNTs in the spraying method.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced polymer matrix composite laminated structure has been widely used in automobiles, ships and aircrafts manufacturing industry due to its high specific strength and specific modulus. Obvious anisotropy manifests in carbon fiber reinforced polymer matrix composite laminates, resulting in the excellent physical and mechanical properties along the axial direction of fiber, such as high in-plane tensile strength and modulus. However, the composite laminates are prone to damage with poor lateral and interlayer performance [1]. Studies have showed that the macroscopic damage of composite laminates is the result of accumulation of internal crack propagation, fiber fracture and interlaminar crack [2-3]. Therefore, it is an effective approach to enhance interlaminar toughness and crack resistance for improving comprehensive performance of composite materials.

Currently, the performance of composite laminates can be improved by three-dimension (3D) technology or adding nanomaterials, ductile interlayers and whiskers between layers [2, 4-6], in which CNTs are a popular choice as a kind of material with high specific strength and specific modulus. When distributed at the crack front, CNTs can bridge resin and fiber and absorb energy by pulling out and breaking, thus slowing down the propagation of cracks [6]. CNTs have a huge potential to enhance interlaminar properties of carbon fiber/epoxy composite and provide an important approach to improve interlayer physical properties such as electrical conductivity. So lots of studies have been done in this field.

The methods of adding CNTs into composite materials can be summarized as following. (1) Adding

CNTs into resin matrix [6-11]. Kostopoulos [8] dispersed multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) into bisphenol A resin to prepare carbon fiber/epoxy composite laminates, finding out that the compression modulus after impact, compression strength and compression-fatigue life were all improved. Behnam Ashrafi [11] attached CNTs to resin by chemical bonds and made carbon fiber/epoxy composite laminates by vacuum infusion process, discovering that the compression strength after impact, Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness (G_{IC}) and Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness (G_{IIC}) were increased by 3.5%, 13% and 28%, respectively. (2) Modifying fibers directly by CNTs[12-14]. E.T.Thostenson[12] grew CNTs on the surface of carbon fiber by chemical vapor deposition, effectively enhancing the interfacial stress transfer efficiency. (3) Modifying prepreg surface by CNTs[15-17]. Faustino Mujika[16] sprayed functionalized MWCNTs suspension on the prepreg surface and prepared 0.1wt% CNTs modified carbon fiber/epoxy composite materials, finding out the initial value of G_{IIC} increased by 22% and the extension value of G_{IIC} increased by 14%. Due to simple process which is harmless to carbon fiber body and easy to industrialize, the above method 1 and method 3 attracted extensive attentions of industry community. However, there still lack further research about the effect of different functionalization of CNTs and different adding methods of CNTs on performance of carbon fiber/epoxy composite materials, which plays an important role in revealing the mechanism of CNTs toughening carbon fiber/epoxy composite materials and technology application.

In this paper, directly adding CNTs into resin and spraying CNTs on the surface of prepreg were adopted to prepare CNTs modified carbon fiber/epoxy composite prepreg to improve interlaminar toughness of carbon fiber/epoxy composite materials. The effect of functionalization of CNTs on resin properties, interface between fiber and resin and interlaminar fracture toughness of composite laminates were evaluated. Besides, the effects of the two adding methods on the interlaminar properties of composite laminates were compared to discuss the advantages and disadvantages of two methods.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

The non-functionalized-CNTs, carboxyl-CNTs (CNTs-COOH) and amino-CNTs (CNTs-NH₂) used in this work are all MWCNTs with diameters in a range of 20~30nm and length between 700nm and 800nm (Suzhou Institute of Nano-Tech and Nano-Bionics, Chinese Academy of Sciences). Figure 1 shows the morphology of CNTs. Carbon fiber/epoxy prepreg had a planar density of 250g/m² and resin content of 34wt.%, which was made of T700SC carbon fibers (Toray Company, Japan) and epoxy 603 resin (Aerospace Research Institute of Materials & Processing Technology, China).

Figure 1: TEM images of CNTs

2.2 Preparation of CNTs modified carbon fiber/epoxy prepreg

CNTs modified carbon fiber/epoxy prepreg was fabricated by directly adding CNTs into resin and spraying method, respectively. For the former, carbon fibers were impregnated by CNTs modified resin homogeneously mixed by three-mill method. For the later, carboxyl-CNTs were dispersed in alcohol and the suspension was sprayed onto the surface of prepreg.

2.3 Preparation of CNTs modified carbon fiber/epoxy composite laminates

CNTs modified carbon fiber/epoxy prepreg was cured in an autoclave according to processing conditions showed in Figure 2. Moreover, a polytetrafluoroethylene film was placed in the middle of prepreg layers as a precrack for the interlaminar fracture toughness testing.

Figure 2: Curing process of CNTs modified carbon fiber/epoxy prepreg

2.4 Characterizations

The curing temperature, heat released from curing process and glass transition temperature (T_g) were tested by Mettler Toledo DSC-1 system with a heating rate of 10 °C /min from 25 °C to 300 °C. Midpoint temperature of glass transition was selected as T_g . Moreover, rheological properties of resin were measured on Gemini Rotational Rheometer (Bohlin Instrument) by stress control mode with frequency of 1Hz, stress of 10Pa and heating rate of 5 °C /min. Chemical reaction between CNTs and sizing agent was characterized by fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) recorded using a Nexus 470 FTIR Spectrometer (Nicolet, USA). Interfacial bonding strength was evaluated by micro-droplet method on Model HM410 composite material interface detector (Tohei Sangyo Corporation, Japan).

Fracture toughness (K_{IC}) of resin was tested on Instron 3344 using single-edge-notch bending (SENB) specimens in accordance with ASTM D5045-99 standard with loading rate of 10mm/min. K_{IC} was calculated according to the following formulas:

$$K_{IC} = \left(\frac{P_Q}{BW^{1/2}} \right) f(x) \quad (1)$$

$$f(x) = 6x^{1/2} \left[\frac{1.99 - x(1-x)(2.15 - 3.93x + 2.7x^2)}{(1+2x)(1-x)^{3/2}} \right] \quad (2)$$

Where $x = a/W$; K_{IC} = fracture toughness of the resin, MPa m^{1/2}; P_Q = maximum load, kN; B = specimen thickness, mm; W = specimen width, mm; a = crack length, mm.

In this paper, the generation difficulty of delamination cracks, also known as interlaminar fracture toughness, was represented by the energy needed to produce mode I crack (opening mode crack) and mode II crack (sliding mode crack), which is characterized by the initial value of G_{IC} and G_{IIC} .

According to ASTM D 5528-01 standard, G_{IC} tests were applied to double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens on Instron 5565 testing machine with loading rate of 1mm/min. The experimental data was revised by modified beam theory (MBT) method and G_{IC} was calculated according to the following formula:

$$G_{IC} = \frac{3p\delta}{2b(a + |\Delta|)} \quad (3)$$

where G_{IC} = Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness, J/m²; P = load, N; δ = load point displacement, m; b = specimen width, m; a = delamination length, m; Δ = intercept of a axis of plot of $C^{1/3}$ ($C = \delta/P$) versus a .

End notched flexure (ENF) specimens were used to determine G_{IIC} on Instron 3382 testing machine with loading rate of 1mm/min according to HB7403-96 standard. G_{IIC} was calculated according to the following formula:

$$G_{IIC} = \frac{9P\delta a^2}{2W(2L^3 + 3a^3)} \times 10^3 \quad (4)$$

where G_{IIC} = Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness, J/m^2 ; P = critical load of crack propagation, N; δ = load point displacement corresponding to P , m; a = valid delamination length, m; W = specimen width, m; $2L$ = span, m.

The morphology of CNTs were observed by JEOL 2100F Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM). Besides, fracture morphology of CNTs modified carbon fiber/epoxy composite laminates was acquired by Apollo 300 Scanning Electron Microscopy (CamScan, UK).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Effect of functionalization of CNTs on interlaminar properties of composite laminates

The code of resin sample were listed in Table 1. The composite laminates researched in this section were all prepared by directly adding CNTs into resin and had the same code with the corresponding resin.

Sample	CNTs functionalization type	CNTs mass fraction/ %
R-0	-	0
R-CNT	Non-functionalized CNTs	1.0
R-COOH	Carboxyl-CNTs	1.0
R-NH ₂	Amino-CNTs	1.0

Table 1: The code of different resin and composite laminates sample

3.1.1 Effect of functionalization of CNTs on resin properties

Rheological properties of resin containing different CNTs were shown in Figure 3. Figure 3a shows viscosity-temperature curve of resins containing different CNTs. It can be found that CNTs can affect the gel temperature of resin. Under the condition of same contents and dimension, non-functionalized CNTs lowered the gel temperature, while amino-CNTs made a rise in resin gel temperature, but carboxyl-CNTs caused no obvious difference. Moreover, it is demonstrated that the addition of CNTs increase the viscosity of resin (shown in Figure 3b) because CNTs hinder the movement of resin molecular chain. However, viscosity of resin containing carboxyl-CNTs and amino-CNTs decreased compared with neat resin because functionalized CNTs had good chemical affinity with resin, thus achieving homogeneous dispersion.

Figure 3: The effect of functionalization of CNTs on resin viscosity: (a) viscosity-temperature curve; (b) low viscosity platform

Due to the reactions between resin and functional groups of CNTs and blockade of CNTs to resin molecular chain motion, CNTs could affect the curing behavior of resin, thus affecting the other performance of the resin and composite laminates. It can be seen from Table 2, the initial curing temperature, peak temperature of the resin and ending temperature of resin increase to a certain degree after the addition of CNTs, whereas the increases are not obvious. However, heat released during curing process declines, in which heat released from the resin containing CNTs-NH₂ is the highest. On one hand, the space steric effect of CNTs influenced the crosslinking of the resin in the curing process. On the other hand, the active hydrogen in -COOH and -NH₂ would react with epoxy groups, thus decreasing the crosslinking point of resin and heat released in curing process.

Sample	R-0	R-CNT	R-COOH	R-NH ₂
Initial curing temperature/ °C	221.70	222.18	228.96	227.26
Peak curing temperature/ °C	272.90	274.34	274.06	275.85
Ending curing temperature/ °C	286.98	288.87	287.52	289.75
Liberation of heat in curing process/(J g ⁻¹)	472.08	440.99	466.49	426.55
T _g / °C	208.53	209.25	207.34	212.26

Table 2: The curing characteristic parameters and T_g of different resin

T_g of different resin are shown in Table 2. By contrast, it can be found that there are no obvious changes in T_g after the addition of non-functionalized CNTs, CNTs-COOH or CNTs-NH₂. The previous analysis shows that the addition of CNTs affects the curing reaction of resin in a certain extent, especially the CNTs- NH₂. This effect would lower the T_g of resin. From another point of view, CNTs would hinder the movement of resin molecular chain, causing higher energy needed by molecular chain motion. In addition, reactive hydrogen in -NH₂ and -COOH can react with epoxy group in resin, making the blocking effect of CNTs stronger, thus increasing the T_g. Based on the above two kinds of effects, T_g of R-CNT and R-COOH don't change much compared with R-0, and T_g of R-NH₂ increases slightly.

It can be seen from Figure 4, the fracture toughness (K_{IC}) of resin is improved by the addition of CNTs, confirming the toughening effect of CNTs. Compared with R-0, K_{IC} of R-CNT increases by 14.17% while that of R-COOH increases by 40.16%. The results show that CNTs-COOH has better toughening effect.

Figure 4: K_{IC} of different resin

3.1.2 Effect of functionalization of CNTs on interface between fiber and resin

The effect of functionalization of CNTs on interface between fiber and resin was explored including the chemical reaction between CNTs and sizing agent and interfacial bonding strength between different resin and carbon fiber.

Different functionalized CNTs were mixed with sizing agent extracted from the surface of carbon fiber, followed by heating at 180°C for 2h. Afterwards, Sizing agent and mixtures of CNTs and sizing

agent before and after heating treatment were characterized by FTIR to inspect chemical reactions between them. The FTIR spectra are showed in Figure 5. It can be found that there is no obvious difference between peaks pattern of different system, and heating treatment could change peak intensity.

Peak of epoxy groups, vibration peak of hydroxyl, bending and stretching vibration peak of ether bond were selected to analysis by infrared analysis software in this work, corresponding to peaks at 915cm^{-1} , 3440cm^{-1} , 1043cm^{-1} and 1180cm^{-1} , respectively. Vibration peak of benzene at 1510cm^{-1} was chosen as interior label and other groups concentration was represented by the ratio of peak height to vibration peak concentration of benzene. The results show that the concentration of $-\text{OH}$ and $-\text{O}-$ increased and the concentration of the epoxy group decreases after heating treatment because of curing reaction of sizing agent. For pure sizing agent, the concentration of epoxy group reduces by 0.024 and the concentration of $-\text{OH}$ and $-\text{O}-$ increases in a certain degree. For sizing agent containing non-functionalized CNTs, the concentration of epoxy group decreases by 0.019, less than pure sizing agent, which is because non-functionalized CNTs has no functional groups that can react with sizing agent and the steric effect of CNTs influences curing reaction of sizing agent. For sizing agent containing CNTs-COOH, the concentration of epoxy group declines by 0.037 and the concentration increases of $-\text{OH}$ and $-\text{O}-$ are higher than that of pure sizing agent, demonstrating that $-\text{COOH}$ on surface of CNTs reacted with sizing agent and produced $-\text{OH}$ and $-\text{O}-$. For sizing agent containing CNTs- NH_2 , the concentration of epoxy group decreases by 0.024 and the concentration of $-\text{OH}$ increases by 0.134, which is the same as pure sizing agent. This may be the integrated effect of steric effect of CNTs to hinder the curing reaction of sizing agent and the reaction between reactive hydrogen of $-\text{OH}$ and epoxy group to promote the curing reaction.

Figure 5: FTIR spectra of different CNTs/sizing agent systems before and after heating treatment

Furthermore, the effects of functionalization of CNTs on interfacial bonding strength were investigated (shown in Figure 6). Comparing interfacial bonding strength between T700SC carbon fiber and different resin, it can be found that R-CNT and R- NH_2 show no obvious difference from R-O, but interfacial bonding strength between carbon fiber and R-COOH significantly increases by 18.52%. The CNTs increase the mechanical engagement between the fiber and resin, which can effectively increase the energy absorbed and path length caused by crack extension at the interface. On the other hand, it is also related to chemical bonds formed between resin and sizing agent on the surface of fiber.

It can be inferred that chemical reactions could occur between -COOH and sizing agent, thus forming chemical bonds between fiber and resin and improving interfacial bonding strength.

Figure 6: Interfacial bonding strength between carbon fiber and different resin

3.1.3 Effect of functionalization of CNTs on interlaminar properties of composite laminates

The initial values of G_{IC} and G_{IIC} of different composite laminates are shown in Figure 7. The results show that there are no evident changes in mode I interlaminar fracture toughness of different CNTs modified composite laminates. This may be due to the low contents of CNTs, causing few CNTs distributed at the front of crack, which could not effectively hinder the crack generation and propagation. However, significant changes in initial value of G_{IIC} happen after adding different CNTs. Different from opening mode cracks in G_{IC} , the ease of generation of sliding mode cracks in G_{IIC} has close relationship with the state and performance of stagger plane. The stagger plane area of sliding mode cracks is usually larger than the area of opening mode crack surface, resulting in significant improvements of G_{IIC} by adding CNTs

Compared with R-0 laminate, the initial values of G_{IIC} of R-CNTs and R-COOH laminates increase by 8.5% and 21.8%, respectively, which is mainly due to the prevention effect of CNTs distributed at the crack front on the crack generation and propagation. Apart from this, previous analysis of the effect of functionalization of CNTs on interface between fiber and resin shows that CNTs-COOH could evidently enhance the interfacial bonding strength, thus improving the mode II interlaminar fracture toughness. Moreover, it is known that the addition of CNTs-NH₂ makes the curing exotherm of resin declined distinctly, thus decreasing the curing degree of resin. The effect of reduced curing degree of resin may be more important than the hinder effect of CNTs on the crack generation and propagation, making the initial value of G_{IIC} of R-NH₂ laminate a little lower than that of R-0 laminate.

Figure 7: Interlaminar fracture toughness of different CNTs modified carbon fiber/epoxy composite laminate: (a) the initial value of G_{IC} ; (b) the initial value of G_{IIC}

Figure 8 and 9 show the fracture morphology of composite laminates with different functionalization of CNTs for G_{IC} test and G_{IIC} test, respectively. It can be seen from the morphology diagrams that smooth section was formed along the fiber direction in R-0 laminate, while rough surface was formed at the fracture area in laminates toughened by CNTs. In CNTs modified composite laminates, irregular distribution of a large amount of resin can be observed, part of which was bonded with fiber surface. It demonstrated that the addition of CNTs can effectively enhance bonding of fiber and resin, improve the performance of interlayer rich resin area and increase the path of crack propagation, thus effectively improving the interlaminar toughness of composite materials.

Figure 8: SEM of fractured G_{IC} composite laminate samples with different functionalization of CNTs

Figure 9: SEM of fractured G_{IIC} composite laminate samples with functionalization of different CNTs

3.2 Effect of adding method of CNTs on interlaminar properties of composite laminates

3.2.1 Spraying method

Spraying CNTs suspension onto carbon fiber/epoxy prepreg by a spray gun is called spraying method. In this case, CNTs-COOH were dispersed in alcohol and the suspension was sonicated for half an hour. Then, the suspension was sprayed onto the surface of prepreg uniformly by a spray gun. Finally, the solvent was evaporated at room temperature. When the solvent was totally evaporated, CNTs modified carbon fiber/epoxy prepreg was completed. CNTs modified prepreg with precrack was cured in an autoclave. And composite laminates were produced by directly adding carboxyl-CNTs into resin of different mass fraction as comparison. For spraying method, the CNTs content was characterized by CNTs areal density. The codes and corresponding parameters of CNTs modified composite laminates were shown in Table 4.

Sample	CNTs mass fraction/wt. %	Sample	CNTs content/ (g m^{-2})
R-0.5	0.5	S-0.38	0.38
R-1.0	1.0	S-0.75	0.75
R-1.5	1.5	S-1.50	1.50
R-2.0	2.0	S-2.25	2.25

Table 4: The code of CNTs-carbon fiber/epoxy composites with different CNTs content

3.2.2 Comparison of different methods

Figure 10 shows the initial value of G_{IC} of different CNTs modified carbon fiber/epoxy composite laminates. It can be found that directly adding CNTs into resin has no obvious difference in the initial

values of G_{IC} of R-0.5, R-1.0 and R-1.5 laminates, but the initial value of G_{IC} of R-2.0 laminate increases by 23.66%. Meanwhile, for spraying method, the initial values of G_{IC} of S-0.38, S-0.75 and S-1.50 laminates significantly improve by 25.87%, 22.57% and 10.37% compared with R-0 laminate, respectively. Nevertheless, the initial value of G_{IC} of S-2.25 laminate is almost same as that of R-0.

Figure 10: Initial value of G_{IC} of different CNTs-carbon fiber/epoxy laminates

For directly adding CNTs into resin, the existence of CNTs can increase the crack propagation path, but CNTs cannot effectively prevent the crack generation and propagation at a low content due to the small amount of CNTs distributed at the crack front. Therefore, there is no evident increase in the initial value of G_{IC} at a low CNT content until 2wt.%. However, for spraying method, the energy needed for crack generation and propagation is significantly increased at a low CNT content because CNTs directly distributed in the interlayer region with high utilization degree. With the increase of the CNTs content, agglomeration would emerge, decreasing the prevent ability for crack generation and propagation and influencing the curing properties of resin.

Figure 11 shows the initial value of G_{IIC} of different CNTs modified carbon fiber/epoxy composite laminates. By contrast, it can be found that for the generation of sliding mode cracks, the initial values of G_{IIC} of R-0.5 and R-1.0 laminates increase by 9.88% and 21.80% respectively while those of R-1.5 and R-2.0 laminates decrease by 14.28% and 21.44% respectively. For the spraying method, the initial values of G_{IIC} of S-0.38, S-0.75, S-1.50 and S-2.25 laminates respectively improve by 23.01%, 36.56%, 15.63% and 21.94%.

Figure 11: Value of initiation G_{IIC} of different CNTs-carbon fiber/epoxy laminates

For spraying method, CNTs were directly distributed in the interlayer area, which effectively increase the energy needed to power interlayer staggered, thus obviously promote the initial value of G_{IIC} . Whereas with the increase of CNTs content, the agglomeration of CNTs could also degrade inhibitory effect of crack generation, thus influencing the interlaminar toughening effect.

From the above, directly adding CNTs into resin as well as spraying CNTs on the prepreg surface can improve the interlaminar performance of carbon fiber/epoxy composite. CNTs were distributed in whole composite laminates with high distribution uniformity by directly adding into resin, thus enhancing the stability of toughening effect and reducing the data dispersion degree. However, its CNTs utilization degree is lower than that in spraying method. Whereas the interlaminar toughness of carbon fiber/epoxy composite materials can be effectively improved at a low content of CNTs by spraying method because CNTs are mainly distributed in the interlayer area.

4 CONCLUSION

(1) Compared with pure epoxy resin, the addition of CNTs reduces the heat released in curing process and lowers curing degree of resin, which is related to the hinder effect of CNTs on resin molecular motion and the chemical reaction between epoxy group and reactive hydrogen in $-\text{COOH}$ and $-\text{NH}_2$. The fracture toughness of resin is improved after adding CNTs, especially the CNTs-COOH.

(2) Functional groups on the CNT surface reacted with epoxy groups in sizing agent, and the reaction degree of CNTs-COOH and sizing agent was evidently higher than that of CNTs-NH₂. As a result, CNTs-COOH effectively enhanced the interfacial bonding strength between carbon fiber and resin by 18.52%.

(3) The functionalization of CNTs had no obvious change on G_{IC} of carbon fiber/epoxy composite laminates, while functionalized CNTs effectively improved the G_{IIC} of composite laminates at a low content (1wt.%). In this work, CNTs-COOH has obvious toughening effect, which enhances the G_{IC} of composite laminates by 21.80%.

(4) For opening mode crack, the G_{IC} of CNTs modified carbon fiber/epoxy composite laminates prepared by directly adding CNTs into resin did not increase until the CNT content increased to 2wt.%. For spraying method, G_{IC} was evidently improved at low CNT content in that CNTs were directly distributed at interlayer area. The G_{IC} of composite laminate was increased the most by 25.87% when the areal density of CNTs was 0.38g/m².

(5) For sliding mode crack, the G_{IIC} of CNTs modified carbon fiber/epoxy composite laminates prepared by directly adding CNTs into resin increased the most by 21.80% at CNT content of 1wt.%. When the CNT areal density was 0.75g/m², the G_{IIC} of composite laminate prepared by spraying method was enhanced the most by 36.56%.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by funding from the National Natural Science Fund Program of China (Grant No. 51103003).

REFERENCES

- [1] Joshi S C, Dikshit V. Enhancing interlaminar fracture characteristics of woven CFRP prepreg composites through CNT dispersion[J]. *Journal of Composite Materials*, 2012, 46(6): 665-675.
- [2] Lubineau G, Rahaman A. A review of strategies for improving the degradation properties of laminated continuous-fiber/epoxy composites with carbon-based nanoreinforcements[J]. *Carbon*, 2012, 50(7): 2377-2395.
- [3] Veedu V P, Cao A, Li X, et al. Multifunctional composites using reinforced laminae with carbon-nanotube forests[J]. *Nature materials*, 2006, 5(6): 457-462.
- [4] Partridge I K, Cartié D D R. Delamination resistant laminates by Z-Fiber[®] pinning: Part I manufacture and fracture performance[J]. *Composites Part A: applied science and manufacturing*, 2005, 36(1): 55-64.
- [5] Zhang X, Hounslow L, Grassi M. Improvement of low-velocity impact and compression-after-impact performance by z-fibre pinning[J]. *Composites science and technology*, 2006, 66(15): 2785-2794.
- [6] Shen Z, Bateman S, Wu D Y, et al. The effects of carbon nanotubes on mechanical and thermal properties of woven glass fibre reinforced polyamide-6 nanocomposites[J]. *Composites Science*

- and Technology*, 2009, 69(2): 239-244.
- [7] Böger L, Sumfleth J, Hedemann H, et al. Improvement of fatigue life by incorporation of nanoparticles in glass fibre reinforced epoxy[J]. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 2010, 41(10): 1419-1424.
- [8] Kostopoulos V, Baltopoulos A, Karapappas P, et al. Impact and after-impact properties of carbon fibre reinforced composites enhanced with multi-wall carbon nanotubes[J]. *Composites Science and Technology*, 2010, 70(4): 553-563.
- [9] Zhu Lili, Gu Yizhuo, Sun Zhijie, et al. Effects of dispersing methods on the properties of low content of carbon nanotube glass fiber /epoxy resin laminates[J]. *Acta Materiae Compositae Sinica*, 2012, 29(5): 11-17.
- [10] Zhao Yanwen, Gu Yizhuo, Li Min, et al. Double vacuum assisted resin infusion molding and property of carbon nanotube –glass fiber/epoxy resin laminates[J]. *Acta Materiae Compositae Sinica*, 2011, 28(3): 13-19.
- [11] Ashrafi B, Guan J, Mirjalili V, et al. Enhancement of mechanical performance of epoxy/carbon fiber laminate composites using single-walled carbon nanotubes[J]. *Composites science and technology*, 2011, 71(13): 1569-1578.
- [12] Thostenson E T, Li W Z, Wang D Z, et al. Carbon nanotube/carbon fiber hybrid multiscale composites[J]. *Journal of Applied Physics*, 2002, 91(9): 6034-6037.
- [13] Sager R J, Klein P J, Lagoudas D C, et al. Effect of carbon nanotubes on the interfacial shear strength of T650 carbon fiber in an epoxy matrix[J]. *Composites Science and Technology*, 2009, 69(7): 898-904.
- [14] Laachachi A, Vivet A, Nouet G, et al. A chemical method to graft carbon nanotubes onto a carbon fiber[J]. *Materials Letters*, 2008, 62(3): 394-397.
- [15] Almuhammadi K, Alfano M, Yang Y, et al. Analysis of interlaminar fracture toughness and damage mechanisms in composite laminates reinforced with sprayed multi-walled carbon nanotubes[J]. *Materials & Design*, 2014, 53: 921-927.
- [16] Mujika F, Vargas G, Ibarretxe J, et al. Influence of the modification with MWCNT on the interlaminar fracture properties of long carbon fiber composites[J]. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 2012, 43(3): 1336-1340.
- [17] Williams J, Graddage N, Rahatekar S. Effects of plasma modified carbon nanotube interlaminar coating on crack propagation in glass epoxy composites[J]. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 2013, 54: 173-181.
- [18] He Z, Zhang X, Chen M, et al. Effect of the filler structure of carbon nanomaterials on the electrical, thermal, and rheological properties of epoxy composites[J]. *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, 2013, 129(6): 3366-3372.
- [19] Wang An-zhi, Chen Long, Hou Wei, et al. Effect of Carbon Nanotubes Incorporation on the Cure Reaction of Epoxy Resin Detected by DSC [J]. *Polymer Materials Science And Engineering*, 2007, 23(2): 157-160.
- [20] Cole K C, Hechler J J, Noel D. A new approach to modeling the cure kinetics of epoxy/amine thermosetting resins. 2. Application to a typical system based on bis [4-(diglycidylamino) phenyl] methane and bis (4-aminophenyl) sulfone[J]. *Macromolecules*, 1991, 24(11): 3098-3110.